

Chloroanilines as corrosion inhibitors for zinc in nitric acid

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Manuscript received 9 March 2004, revised 21 April 2005, accepted 20 May 2005

The inhibition by chloro-substituted anilines on corrosion of zinc in nitric acid has been studied in relation to acid concentration, inhibitors concentration and temperature. The corrosion increases with acid concentration and with increase of temperature. The mode of the inhibition appears to be chemisorption. Zinc in 0.05 M HNO₃ shows a corrosion potential as -920 mV. Galvanostatic polarization curves shows both anodic and cathodic polarization.

Zinc is one of the most vital non-ferrous metal, find extensive use in metallic coating. Various aromatic amines¹, chloro substituted anilines², thio compounds³ etc. have been used as corrosion inhibitors for zinc in nitric acid solutions. The present study was undertaken to understand the corrosion behaviour of zinc in nitric acid containing chloroanilines as inhibitors.

Results and discussion

To assess the effect of corrosion of zinc in nitric acid, chloroanilines are added as inhibitors and their inhibition efficiency (IE) has been calculated as follows :

$$IE\% = \frac{W_u - W_i}{W_u} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where, W_u is the weight loss of metal in uninhibited acid and W_i is the weight loss of metal in inhibited acid.

The rate of corrosion increases with the increase in acid concentration. The corrosion rate was 250.7, 1590.3, 3258.5 and 5132.3 mg/dm² in 0.01, 0.05, 0.10 and 0.15 M HNO₃ concentration respectively for a period of 24 h at 301 ± 1 K as shown in Table 1. To assess their protective value, aromatic amines like *ortho*, *meta* and *para*-chloroaniline were added having 10, 20, 30 and 40 mM concentration in 0.01, 0.05, 0.10 and 0.15 M HNO₃ concentration (Table 1). At constant acid concentration, the IE of the chloroanilines increases with the inhibitor concentration, e.g. in the case of *o*-chloroaniline for 0.15 M HNO₃, the IE was found to be 67, 84, 85 and 90% with respect to 10, 20, 30 and 40 mM inhibitor concentration respectively (Table 1).

Effect of acid concentration : At constant inhibitor concentration, the IE increases with the increase in acid concentration, e.g. 40 mM inhibitor concentration, the IE of *o*-

Table 1. Corrosion rate (CR) and inhibition efficiency (IE) of zinc in 0.01, 0.05, 0.10 and 0.15 M HNO₃ containing chloroanilines as inhibitors for an immersion period of 24 h at 301 ± 1 K

System	Inhibitor conc. (mm)	Concentration of nitric acid							
		0.01 M		0.05 M		0.1 M		0.15 M	
		CR mg/dm ²	IE %	CR mg/dm ²	IE %	CR mg/dm ²	IE %	CR mg/dm ²	IE %
A	-	250.7	-	1590.3	-	3258.5	-	5132.3	-
B	10	128.8	48	642.7	59	1162.6	64	1649.3	67
	20	110.1	56	543.5	66	595.5	81	850.6	83
	30	89.8	64	491.5	69	567.1	83	782.1	85
	40	80.6	68	392.2	75	415.9	87	498.6	90
C	10	150.1	40	817.6	48	1592.6	51	1923.4	62
	20	135.2	46	699.4	56	633.3	80	935.7	82
	30	55.8	62	500.9	58	614.4	81	845.9	83
	40	90.0	64	425.3	73	519.8	84	538.7	89
D	10	179.6	28	902.6	43	2126.2	34	2103.0	59
	20	152.4	39	619.1	61	723.1	77	808.1	84
	30	125.0	50	458.4	71	685.3	79	633.3	87
	40	105.7	58	425.3	73	642.7	80	557.6	89

A = HNO₃, B = HNO₃ + *o*-chloroaniline, C = HNO₃ + *m*-chloroaniline, D = HNO₃ + *p*-chloroaniline.

chloroaniline is 68, 75, 87 and 90% with respect to 0.01, 0.05, 0.10 and 0.15 M acid concentration respectively. Generally at all inhibitor concentrations, *o*-chloroaniline shows better inhibition than *meta* and *para*-chloroaniline (Table 1).

To determine the effect of temperature on corrosion, corrosion rate was measured in 0.15 M HNO₃ containing 10, 20, 30 and 40 mM inhibitor concentration at solution temperature of 303, 313, 323 and 333 K for an immersion period of 2 h. The result in Table 2 shows that corrosion rate decreases with rise in temperature. In 0.15 M HNO₃ at 40 mM inhibitor concentration, the IE for *o*-chloroaniline was 95, 93, 92 and 88% at 303, 313, 323 and 333 K respectively.

Energy of activation (E_a) has been calculated from the slope of $\log \rho$ versus $1/T$ (ρ = corrosion rate, T = absolute temperature) and also with the help of the Arrhenius equation⁴.

$$\log \frac{\rho_2}{\rho_1} = \frac{E_a}{2.303 R} [(1/T_1) - (1/T_2)] \quad (2)$$

where, ρ_1 and ρ_2 are the corrosion rate at temperature T_1 and T_2 respectively.

Mean E_a value given in the Table 2 shows that the E_a value for the corrosion of zinc in 0.15 M HNO₃ is 16.6 kJ/mol. In acid containing inhibitors, the mean E_a values are found to be higher than that of uninhibited system. Mean E_a values are 41.8, 25.2 and 32.3 kJ/mol for *o*-chloroaniline, *m*-chloroaniline and *p*-chloroaniline respectively. The higher values of mean E_a indicates physical adsorption of the inhibitors on metal surface⁵. The values of E_a calculated from the slope of Arrhenius plot and using eq. (2) are almost similar.

The value of heat of adsorption (Q_{ads}) were calculated by the following equation⁴.

$$Q_{ads} = 2.303 R [\log (\theta_2/1 - \theta_2) - \log (\theta_1/1 - \theta_1)] \times [T_1.T_2/T_2 - T_1] \quad (3)$$

where, θ_1 and θ_2 [$\theta = (W_u - W_i)/W_i$] are the fractions of the metal surface covered by the inhibitors at temperature T_1 and T_2 respectively.

The values of the free energy of adsorption (ΔG_a) were calculated with the help of the following equation⁶.

$$\log C = \log (\theta/1 - \theta) - \log B \quad (4)$$

where, $\log B = -1.74 - (\Delta G_a/2.303 RT)$ and C is the inhibitor concentration.

From Table 2, it is evident that in all cases, the Q_{ads} values are negative and lie in the range of -8.5 (*m*-chloroaniline) to -29.1 (*o*-chloroaniline) kJ/mol. As the temperature increases values of Q_{ads} decreases (becomes more negative). The negative Q_{ads} values shows that the adsorption and hence the IE decreases with rise in temperature⁷.

The value of mean ΔG_a are given in Table 2. In all cases, mean ΔG_a values are negative and lie in the range of -13.06 (*m*-chloroaniline) to -13.09 (*o*-chloroaniline) kJ/mol. The most efficient inhibitor shows more negative ΔG_a value.

The value of ΔH (enthalpy of adsorption) and ΔS (entropy of adsorption) were calculated at 40 mM inhibitor concentration in 0.15 M HNO₃ at 303 K (Table 2). The ΔH values are positive, meaning that these processes are endothermic and are favoured at higher temperatures. The ΔS values are also found positive, conforming that the process is entropically favourable⁸.

Potential behaviour : In 0.05 M HNO₃, the potential value for *o*-chloroaniline (-957 mV), *m*-chloroaniline (-940 mV) and *p*-chloroaniline (-925 mV). These values are more negative than the initial potential value of uninhibited acid (-920 mV). Thereafter the potential moves further in positive direction on addition of inhibitors and settles as -974 mV in 40 min for *o*-chloroaniline, -976 mV in 35 min for *m*-chloroaniline and -952 mV in 40 min for *p*-chloroaniline.

Table 2. Effect of temperature on corrosion rate (CR), inhibition efficiency (IE%) for zinc in 0.15 M HNO₃ containing 40 mM chloroanilines as inhibitors

System	Temperature (K)								Mean E_a from eq. (2) (kJ/mol)	E_a from Arrhenius plot (kJ/mol)	Q_{ads} (kJ/mol)			Mean (kJ/mol)		
	303		313		323		333				303-	313-	323-	ΔG	ΔH	ΔS
	CR	IE	CR	IE	CR	IE	CR	IE			313	323	333			
	mg/dm ²	%														
A	1972.4	-	2405.5	-	2767.6	-	3549.1	-	16.6	17.4	-	-	-	-	-	-
B	91.1	95	150.0	93	237.9	92	407.4	88	41.8	42.1	-24.8	-29.1	-28.6	-13.09	36.1	0.16
C	132.1	93	179.5	92	231.6	91	324.0	90	25.2	25.5	-9.1	-10.5	-8.5	-13.06	21.7	0.11
D	108.3	94	179.6	92	231.6	91	344.9	90	32.3	28.1	-25.9	-10.4	-14.7	-13.07	36.4	0.16

Effective area of specimen : 0.2116 dm², immersion period : 2 h.

A = HNO₃, B = HNO₃ + *o*-chloroaniline, C = HNO₃ + *m*-chloroaniline, D = HNO₃ + *p*-chloroaniline.

Table 3. Polarization data and inhibition efficiency (IE%) of chloroaniline for zinc in 0.05 M HNO₃Effective area of specimen : 0.0247 dm², inhibitor concentration : 40 mM

System	E_{corr} (mV)	I_{corr} $\mu\text{A}/\text{sq. cm}$	Tafel slope(mV/decade)			IE% from methods	
			Anodic β_a	Cathodic $-\beta_c$	B mV	Weight loss	By polari- zation
A	-1011	2.45	111.1	200.0	31.1	-	-
B	-1028	0.52	149.8	125.0	29.6	79	78
C	-1031	0.69	125.0	214.2	34.3	72	74
D	-1037	0.72	100.0	789.5	38.9	71	76

A = HNO₃, B = HNO₃ + *o*-chloroaniline, C = HNO₃ + *m*-chloroaniline, D = HNO₃ + *p*-chloroaniline.

Polarization behaviour: Anodic and cathodic galvanostatic polarization curves for zinc in 0.05 M HNO₃ acid, alone and containing 40 mM concentration of chloroanilines are shown in Fig. 1. The curves show polarization of both, the cathodes as well as anodes. IE calculated from corrosion current obtained by extrapolation of the cathodic and anodic Tafel lines are given in Table 3. In almost all the cases, the efficiencies from Tafel plots agree well (within $\pm 5\%$) with the values obtained from weight loss data.

Fig. 1. Polarization curves for corrosion of zinc in 0.05 M nitric acid containing 40 mM inhibitor concentration.

The mechanism of inhibitor of corrosion process is believed to be due to the formation and maintenance of a protective film on the metal surface. Further, when $\log(\theta/1-\theta)$ is plotted against $\log C$ straight lines are obtained. This suggests that the inhibitors cover both the anodic as well as cathodic regions through general adsorption following Langmuir isotherm.

In chloroaniline, substitution of electron attracting -Cl group increases the contribution of the positively charged resonance state of aniline. Thus, increasing its adsorbability at the surface of zinc.

Halogens are exerting both +R and -I effect but +R ef-

fect is very small. Presence of halogens decreases the basicity of NH₂ group due to the -I effect⁹.

Experimental

Rectangular plates (5 × 2 × 0.1 cm) of zinc having an area of 0.2116 dm² are taken. All the specimens were cleaned by buffing and wrapped in plastic bag till use to avoid atmospheric corrosion.

A specimen, suspended by glass hook, was immersed in 230 ml test solution at 301 ± 1 K for 24 h. After the test, the specimens were cleaned by using 10% CrO₃ solution having 0.2% BaCO₃¹⁰. After cleaning, the specimens were washed with distilled water followed by acetone and dried with air dryer. Triplicate experiment were performed in each case and mean value of the weight losses were reported.

To determine the effect of temperature on corrosion, weight loss was measured in 0.15 M HNO₃ containing 40 mM of the inhibitor concentration at solution temperature of 303, 313, 323 and 333 K for a period of 2 h.

For polarization study, metal specimens having an area of 0.0247 dm² were exposed in 500 ml corrosive solution without and with 40 mM inhibitor concentration in 0.05 M HNO₃. The test cell includes the zinc specimen as a working electrode, corrosive solution in which the specimen was to be tested and saturated calomel electrode used as a reference electrode. Two counter electrode were used to supply current flowing the working electrode during the test. The polarization study was made using galvanostat/-potentiostat (EG and PARC model 273). Graphs were plotted between potential vs log current density. Cathodic and anodic polarization curves give cathodic and anodic Tafel lines correspondingly. The intersect point of cathodic and anodic Tafel lines gives the corrosion current (I_{corr}) and the potential (E_{corr}).

Conclusion :

- * As acid concentration increases the corrosion increases.
- * At constant inhibitor concentration, the IE of all inhibitor increases as the concentration of acid increases.
- * At all concentration of acid, as the inhibitor concentration increases IE increases and corrosion rate decreases.
- * The order of inhibition is as follows : *o*-chloroaniline > *m*-chloroaniline > *p*-chloroaniline.
- * Addition of inhibitors in corrosive media indicates that as the temperature increases corrosion rate increases while IE decreases.
- * In all cases, Q_{ads} and ΔG_a values are negative, while ΔH and ΔS values are positive.
- * Mean values of E_a in inhibited acid is higher than the value of E_a in acid only, which shows that chemisorption of the inhibitor molecule.
- * The polarization curves show polarization of both the cathodes as well as the anodes.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Department of Chemistry, Navyug Science College, Surat for providing laboratory facilities.

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